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Board of Directors and Auditor Choice in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study interrogates the tie between board of directors and the choice of the external auditor by 129 listed firms in Nigeria.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Board of directors was represented using board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership. The Big4 methodology was utilized to assess auditor choice using binary analysis. This study collects balanced panel data from 129 listed firms over a five-year period, from 2017 to 2021. All the data were provided by MachameRatios(®).

Findings: Test results suggest that board female gender, size, meetings and ownership have significant relationship with auditor choice. However, board independence and size exhibit no significant associations with auditor choice. Moreover, the mean value of auditor choice is .555 points for the 129 listed companies in Nigeria, over the five years (2017-2021).

Originality: This study contributes to the process of choosing external auditor by companies in Nigeria. It provides value to the company's board of directors, board audit committee members and management in order for them to make better judgments on which external auditor(s) to engage. The results have ramifications for regulatory agencies, market participants, shareholders, lenders, and corporate boards. This study suffers from some limitations. First, the data is from 129 listed firms, over a period of five-years (2017-2021). Second, board of directors' proxies are limited to five: board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership. Other board characteristics such as expertise, remuneration, busyness, education, and committees are not included. Third, the results are applicable to the sample, Nigerian publicly companies, and emerging countries with similar institutional framework like Nigeria.

KEYWORDS

Board of directors, board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings, board ownership, auditor choice, big4, listed firms, Nigeria

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CLASSIFICATION

G34, G320

I. Introduction

The choice of external auditor(s) for a firm is as important as successfully running a corporation. This statement of facts apply to both developed and developing countries for a going concern company, where the interests of shareholders are prioritized. The appointment of external auditor(s) is part of corporate governance mechanisms put in place to prevent corporate managers from allowing their interests to clash with the interests of shareholders.

Auditors are engaged in order to scrutinize and express opinion on the accounts and reports prepared by the managers of companies, in terms of compliance with accounting standards, and in the present case, the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) at the level of publicly listed firms and International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) at the level of government establishments. In Nigeria, publicly listed firms were required to comply with IFRS since the beginning of year 2012. However, government

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establishments were required to comply with IPSAS since the beginning of 2014. Perhaps, it is instructive to state that despite the several benefits associated with the engagement of quality external auditors, the decision to engage, which external auditor(s) has become a source of concern, or to say the least, problematic for corporate stakeholders, particularly, regulators, and shareholders. This is the motivation of this study; since corporations have Nigeria face two options: to appoint external auditor(s) from the Big4 (PWC, Deloitte, KPMG, and Ernst and Young) or to appoint non-Big4 external auditors.

There are growing concerns about the choice of a firm external auditor(s) and several factors are responsible for this situation. This has generate inconclusiveness, resulting in more research. Auditor choice has been examined by a number of scholars, particularly, outside Nigeria (Alsayani et al., 2023; Bhattacharya & Banerjee, 2020; Citron & Manalis, 2001; DeAngelo, 1982; Feltham et al., 1991; Guedhami et al., 2009; Habib et al., 2019; Hsu et al., 2018; Johansen & Pettersson, 2013; Mardini & Tahat, 2017). However, there are few empirical papers in Nigeria that discuss auditor choice (Adeyemi & Uadiale, 2011; Emeh & Appah, 2013; Mgbame et al., 2012; Olagunju, 2011; Soyemi, 2020). This is the scenario in Nigeria despite the role of the external auditor(s) in the process of preparation of a firm annual reports and accounts, before, they are presented to the shareholders.

Board of directors, as stated earlier is one of the corporate governance mechanisms, constituted to oversee managers. Other corporate governance mechanisms include regulators, ownership structure and, auditors. This is due to agency issues arising from managers having different interests from that of owners (shareholders). So, the owners set up a board of directors to oversee the managers, from time to time at least, meeting four times, in a year, to review the activities of the chief executive officer and executive directors. As a result, board of directors has become the most critical aspect of all corporations.

It contributes to the regular and proper supervision, and control efficiency, and effectiveness, thereby reducing agency conflicts between shareholders and managers. The board of directors is responsible for governance, oversight, and major decision-making, representing the interests of shareholders or stakeholders. The chief executive officer (CEO) is hired and evaluated by the board of directors. The CEO executes board-approved strategies, manage resources, and lead the executive team. Therefore, all businesses should focus on establishing a sound board of directors.

Board of directors plays significant roles in this progression as the structure is responsible for shareholders, on one hand, and managers, on the other hand. Board of directors is characterized in this paper with five attributes (board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership).

A number of previous studies have examined the nexus between board of directors and auditor choice (Alfraih, 2017; Bhattacharya & Banerjee, 2020; Habib et al., 2019; Johansen & Pettersson, 2013; Mak & Roush, 2000). Therefore, this study provides additional information on the relationship between the board of directors of a firm and the external auditor(s) choice decisions.

This study is important for a number of reasons: it provides information to stakeholders in the areas of policy formulation, performance improvement and future research. However, in terms of scoping, it covers five years (2017-2021) and the variables are: independent variables (board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership), dependent variable (Big4) and control variables (firm leverage and firm size). The remaining sections are organized into four (4) sections, covering literature review, methodology, results and discussion and conclusions and recommendations. Section two (2), which is the literature review covers conceptual literature, theoretical literature and empirical literature. The section three (3), covers the research design, population, sample, model specification, variables definitions, measurements and sources; methods of data collection and analysis.

Section four (4) covers descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section five (5) covers conclusions and recommendations.

II. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

The agency theory has been widely used in several studies by scholars to provide theoretical understanding of what determines the nexus between board of directors and auditor choice. Essentially, agency theory opines that a firm board of directors exists in order to protect the interests of shareholders. Agency theory, thus, focuses in resolving the conflicts of interest between shareholders and management. Therefore, the theoretical framework for this study will be explained by the agency theory. The agency theory is the most widely used theory to explain the role of board of directors in companies as a going concern. Agency theory proposes that the shareholders are principals, while the management of the firm are the agents. To put it more clearly, agency theory is a principle that is used to explain and resolve issues in the relationship between business principals and their agents. Most commonly, that relationship is the one between shareholders, as principals, and company executives, as agents.

The theoretical framework as shown in Figure 1 shows the framework for this study. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (auditor choice) and the independent variable (board of directors), which is proxied by board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership. The analytical framework in Figure 1 will lead to further articulation of the model specification in section 3 (methodology).

Fig 1 Analytical Framework

Auditor choice is seen in this paper as, audit firm from Big4 or otherwise. This is similar to the works of scholars outside Nigeria (Alsayani et al., 2023; Bhattacharya & Banerjee, 2020; Citron & Manalis, 2001; DeAngelo, 1982; Feltham et al., 1991; Guedhami et al., 2009; Habib et al., 2019; Hsu et al., 2018; Johansen & Pettersson, 2013; Mardini & Tahat, 2017) and the works of scholars in Nigeria (Adeyemi & Uadiale, 2011; Emeh & Appah, 2013; Mgbame et al., 2012; Olagunju, 2011; Soyemi, 2020).

In addition, board independence is seen in this paper as the proportion of non-executive board of directors relative to board size, expressed as a percentage, as similarly seen by some scholars (Abatecola et al., 2014; Ali & Meah, 2021; Altuwaijri & Kalyanaraman, 2016; Bhagat & Black, 2001; Boone et al., 2007; Chen et al., 2018; Dalton & Dalton, 2005; He et al., 2009; Saibaba, 2013; Wang, 2014).

In the same vein, board female gender is seen in this paper as the number of female directors as a proportion of board size, expressed in percentage. Some scholars have described board female gender in this manner (Boukattaya & Omri, 2021; Dimitropoulos & Koronios, 2021; Guizani & Abdalkrim, 2022; Lanis et al., 2017; Low et al., 2015; Oba & Fodio, 2013; Saeed et al., 2019; Simionescu et al., 2021; Solimene et al., 2017; Wang, 2020).

Furthermore, board size is seen in this paper as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman, Vice Chairman, and CEO/Managing director, Executive Directors, Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary. Some scholars have similarly seen board size in the same context (Bermig & Frick, 2010; Boone et al., 2007; Huther, 1997; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Mayur & Saravanan, 2005; Mayur & Saravanan, 2017; Ning et al., 2007; Ning et al., 2010; Saibaba & Ansari, 2012; Sarpal & Singh, 2013).

Also, board meetings is seen in this paper as the number of board meetings held by the board of directors in a year. Scholars who similarly refers to board meetings as in this paper are listed in this parenthesis (Aanu et al., 2014; Al-Matari et al., 2014; Boesso et al., 2017; Chaudhary & Gakhar, 2018; Dalton & Dalton, 2005; Fariha et al., 2022; Kakanda & Salim, 2017; Narwal & Jindal, 2015; Rahman et al., 2019).

Board ownership is seen in this paper as total directors direct and indirect shares owned divided by total numbers of shares, expressed in percentage. Some scholars also agreed to this definition (Alkurdi & Mardini, 2020; Audretsch & Lehmann, 2005; Barnhart & Rosenstein, 1998; Barontini & Bozzi, 2011; Darmadi & Gunawan, 2013; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Morck et al., 1986; Morck et al., 1988; Ng, 2005; Salehi & Baezgar, 2011).

Furthermore, in terms of control variables, firm leverage is seen in this paper as total liabilities divided by total asset, expressed in percentage. Some scholars have similarly defined leverage in this way (Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Dang, 2011; Dang, 2013; de La Bruslerie & Latrous, 2012; Dewenter & Malatesta, 2001; Jihadi et al., 2021; O'Brien & Vanderheiden, 1987; Padrón et al., 2005; Riechers et al., 2022; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021).

Also, firm size is seen in this paper as the natural logarithm of total assets. Other authors, who similarly, describe firm size in this manner are listed in this parenthesis (Arvanitis, 1997; Berk, 1996; Canback et al., 2006; Cheung & Ng, 1992; Dang et al., 2018; Gallo & Christensen, 2011; Halkos & Tzeremes, 2007; Liu, 1995; Shefer & Frenkel, 2005; Verwaal & Donkers, 2002; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021).

It has been observed the increasing role of board of directors in selecting the external audit firm to carry out audit of the annual accounts and reports of a firm. Hence, it is important to examine empirically the effects of board of directors on auditor choice decision by a firm. Furthermore, prior studies indicate that the total number of occupants on the board of corporate governance is an essential factor in determining the quality of corporate governance.

According to the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code of 2018, every public company should be governed by an effective board that controls, directs, and leads the company. Reviewing the past literature shows that a smaller board size facilitates better communication of information and coordination, hence higher effectiveness in monitoring. However, smaller boards have a less diversified range of expertise than larger

boards, which results in an ineffective quality of advice and monitoring. Furthermore, in general, the proportion of independent non-executive directors to the total number of directors on the board is used to determine the level of board independence. In comparison to non-independent directors, independent directors are more concerned with long-term advantages and have a stronger stakeholder focus. The board should have a mix of Executive and Non-Executive Directors. According to the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code of 2018, a board must have three or two-thirds of the Non-Executive Directors nominated to the board as independent non-executive directors, whichever is greater. Furthermore, Women on the board have become an essential component of good corporate governance. Female directors bring different perspectives and opinions among diverse members of the board to promote better decisions. Female directors effectively enhance the choice of external auditors. Therefore, higher women representation on the board would provide an easy choice of external auditor(s).

According to the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code of 2018, a board must meet at least four (4) times in a fiscal year. Such meetings provide opportunities to the board members to actively and effectively oversight the activities of the CEO/Managing Director and Executive Directors.

Similarly, board ownership has the capacity to motivate board members to ensure that the company is properly directed towards success. Board ownership, also, ensures that directors are committed, because their investments are involved. Thus, a board with shareholdings, is likely to work towards the success of the firm and vice versa.

The subsequent parts in this section cover the breakdown of the main explanatory variables (board of directors) and their causal relationship with the outcome variable (auditor choice).

For example, Lin and Liu (2008) investigate the determinants of firms' auditor choice in China in respect of their corporate governance mechanism. They develop a logit regression model to test the impact of firms' internal corporate governance mechanism on auditor

choice decisions made by IPO firms getting listed during a bear market period of 2001–2004 in China. The empirical results show that firms with larger controlling shareholders, with smaller size are less likely to hire a Top 10 (high-quality) auditor.

Aljabr (2010) empirically examine the effect of greater proportion of nonexecutive board directors on the firm's choice of the external auditor in Saudi Arabia. Using logit regression estimates, the study shows that the presence of more nonexecutive directors has no effect on the choice of auditors in Saudi Arabia. Moreover, the study provides empirical evidence that large firms are more likely to appoint a Big 4 auditor, while highly leveraged firms are less likely to appoint a Big 4 auditor.

Also, Johansen and Pettersson (2013) use unique Danish data to examine whether non-executive directors (board independence) draw on both direct and indirect ties in the network of interlocking directorates to impact auditor choice. The paper finds clear evidence that non-executive directors (board independence) draw on their networks to impact auditor choice.

Soliman and Abdel-Salam (2013) provide evidence on the effectiveness of corporate governance practices and audit quality from a developing country. The data for analysis are gathered from the top 50 most active companies in the Egyptian Stock Exchange, covering the three year period 2007-2009. Logistic regression was used in investigating the questions that were raised in the study. Findings from the study show that board independence significantly have relationship with audit quality. Evidence also exist that size of the company and business leverage are important factors in audit quality for companies quoted on the Egypt Stock Exchange

Ianniello et al. (2013) analyze the relationship between some internal corporate governance characteristics and external auditor choice. They use a sample of Italian listed companies during the period 2007 – 2010. Univariate and multivariate analysis show that board of directors' independence does not play a role in the choice of external auditor. The board of directors' size appears to be positively associated with the choice of a reputed external auditor (Big 4). Overall, a

small board of directors tend to discourage the choice of a reputed auditor.

Karaimrahimoglu (2013) investigates the association between corporate governance and auditor choice by using a sample of 805 firm-year observations from Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE) between the years 2005-2009. Overall findings show that firms' auditor choice in terms of Big-4 and audit firm industry specialization is affected by the firm-level corporate governance mechanisms of firms, particularly, board of directors' composition. Also, Jizi et al. (2013) assert that larger boards of directors would be better able to lead management in auditor choice.

Cho et al. (2014) investigate whether hiring a high-quality auditor (i.e. industry specialist) depends on board size and board independence after controlling a different level of agency conflicts. They use logistic regressions on 12,449 firm-year samples of Taiwanese public companies from 1998 to 2011 by grouping the samples into three categories: low, medium and high agency conflicts. The results show that the board size and independence can explain the decision of auditor selection only in low and medium groups.

Alfraih (2017) investigates the association between the composition of boards of directors and the choice of external auditor among companies listed on the Kuwait Stock Exchange (KSE) in 2013. To accommodate the dichotomous dependent variable (auditor choice), a logistic regression model is used to test the hypothesized associations between board composition and auditor choice. After controlling for firm-specific characteristics, results show that board independence, diversity and size are statistically significant and increase the likelihood that a KSE-listed company selects a high-quality (Big 4) audit firm.

Also, Habib et al. (2019) empirically review archival literature on the determinants of auditor choice in an international setting, critique the findings, and offer suggestions for future research. They categorize the determinants into corporate governance determinants and conclude that board of directors as part of corporate governance characteristics are significant.

Bhattacharya and Banerjee (2020) examine various factors affecting selection of auditors using a sample comprising 22,644 firm-years for 1,366 Indian firms from 1990 to 2015. This paper finds that firms with larger boards and

higher proportion of independent board of directors are more likely to choose a Big 4-affiliated auditor.

By referring to the literature aforementioned, the following hypotheses are formulated and tested:

H₁: There is no significant relationship between board independence and auditor choice.

II. Methodology

This section explains the techniques and approach employed in carrying out the empirical study on the nexus between board of directors' characteristics and auditor choice. To this end, the section begins with the research design, closely followed by the population of the study. This is followed by the sample size and sampling techniques, before the method of data collections which is closely followed by model specification and technique of data analysis. This study uses the correlational research design. The population of the study is based on the companies listed in the Nigerian Exchange (NGX), which was 156 companies, from 11 industries as of 31st December 2022.

However, the study covers only one hundred and twenty-nine (129) listed companies from 11 industry sectors for five years from 2017 to 2021, meaning that 27 firms were excluded. The data was obtained from MachameRatios®. As indicated earlier, the sample size for the study were one hundred and twenty-nine (129) firms (83%). This chosen sample size for the study is thus, consistent or in line with the suggestion made by Kerjice and Morgan (1970) that a minimum of five percent (5%) of a defined population is considered as being adequate sample size required for generalization. The firms in the agricultural sector, construction industry, conglomerates, consumer goods, industrial goods, health care, ICT, financial services, oil and gas sector, natural goods, and services sector are considered.

This study measured auditor choice using the Big4 audit firm (PWC, Deloitte, KPMG, Ernst and Young) as 1, or otherwise 0. All the data were based on the annual reports and accounts published by the firms.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between board female gender and auditor choice.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between board size and auditor choice.

H₄: There is no significant relationship between board meetings and auditor choice.

H₅: There is no significant relationship between board ownership and auditor choice.

Board independence was measured by the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size, expressed in percentage (%). Board female gender was measured as the number of female directors divided by total board size, expressed in percentage (%). Board meetings was measured as the number of board meetings held by the board of directors in a year. Board ownership, also known as board shareholding was measured as total directors direct and indirect shares owned divided by total numbers of shares, expressed in percentage (%). On the control variables, leverage was measured as total liabilities divided by total asset. In similar, firm size was measured as natural logarithm of total asset.

The study uses secondary data (historical data) collected in respect of the variables captured covering the time frame of five years (2017 to 2021) which were obtained from the MachameRatios® database. Several previous studies have used annual financial statements. According to Gray et al. (1995), annual financial statements is the main official and legal document produced by companies on a regular basis and an important medium for their communications. Companies exercise control over the annual financial statements to prevent any possible journalistic information distortion or interpretation (Gray et al., 1995). Furthermore, according to Tilt (2001), financial statements are mandatory by legislation to be regularly produced particularly by all quoted corporate entities and by these facts making comparisons quite easy or simple.

Furthermore, the statistical tool STATA 16 was utilized to apply the aforementioned binary logistic data modeling approach and evaluate the data. Table 1 displays all of the study's variables and measuring procedures.

Operationalization of Variables

Table 1. Operationalization of Variables

Variables	Indicator	Measurement	Source
Independent Variables			
X ₁ = Board independence	Independent executive directors and non-executive directors	Proportion of independent non-executive directors to the total number of directors in the board	Samarakoon et al. (2018)
X ₁ = Board female gender	Number of women in the board	Proportion of women to the total number of directors in the board	Samarakoon et al. (2018)
X ₁ = Board Size	Number of directors	Total number of directors in the board	Madhusanka et al. (2019)
X ₁ = Board meetings	Number of times meetings are held in a fiscal year	Measured as the number of the board meetings held by the board of directors in a year	Aanu et al., 2014; Al-Matari et al., 2014; Boesso et al., 2017
X ₁ = Board ownership	Percentage of shares held by board members	Measured as total directors direct and indirect shares owned divided by total numbers of shares (%)	Alkurdi & Mardini (2020)
Control Variables			
Leverage	Liabilities over total assets	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset	Yahaya (2006)
Firm size	Natural logarithm of total assets	Measured as natural log of total asset	Yahaya (2006)
Dependent Variable			
Auditor Choice (AC)	Presence of Big4 audit firm	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise	Alsayani et al., 2023; Bhattacharya & Banerjee, 2020

Model Specification

To study the relationship between board of directors and auditor choice, the following Panel regression model is formulated and tested:

$$AC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BI_{it} + \beta_2 BG_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 BM_{it} + \beta_5 BO_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} + \beta_7 FS_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where AC is auditor choice, BI is the board independence, BG is the board female gender, BS is the board size, BM is the board meetings, BO is the board ownership, LEV is leverage and FS is firm size. Also, β_0 is intercept, also known as constant, β_{1-7} are beta coefficients, measure the slope of each beta; i is firm script (in this case, i is 129 firms); t is time script (in this case, t is 5 years) and ε is idiosyncratic error term.

Thus, our *a priori* expectations are as follows:

X₁>0: means that a rise in board independence will generate a rise in auditor choice.

X₂>0: means that a rise in board female gender will generate a rise in auditor choice.

X₃>0: means that a rise in board size will generate a rise in auditor choice.

X₄>0: means that a rise in board meetings will generate a rise in auditor choice.

X₅>0: means that a rise in board ownership will generate a rise in auditor choice.

The econometric technique adopted in this study is the Binary Logistic Panel regression technique. The rationale for its usage is based on the following justifications: the dependent variable (auditor choice) is measured by binary (1, 0), that is, the audit firm is a member of Big4 1, otherwise 0, and data that collected have time and cross-sectional attributes that gives room for studying over time (time series) as well as across the sampled firms (cross-section); panel data regression provides better results since it increases sample size and reduces the problem of degree of freedom (Muhammad, 2012). It also avoids the problem of multicollinearity and help to capture the individual cross-sectional (or firm-specific) effects that the various pools may exhibit with respect to the dependent variable in the model.

The individual statistical significance test (T-test) and overall statistical significance test (F-test) are used. Importantly, the goodness of fit of the model is ascertained using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and F-test results. Our binary logistic panel regression analysis is done after descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. All these analyses are conducted at 5% level of significance using STATA 16 software.

IV. Results and Discussions

This section is devoted to results and its discussion. It covers, essentially three components: descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and binary logistic regression. Descriptive statistics are summaries of the variables of interest. They provide opportunities for the reader to easily understand and follow.

Table 2. *Descriptive Statistics*

Variables	obs	Mean	Std Dev.	Min	Max
AC	645	.555	.497	0	1
BI	645	73.433	12.994	16.67	100
BG	645	15.535	13.431	0	66.67
BS	645	9.256	3.163	3	21
BM	645	4.896	1.751	1	16
BO	645	22.254	28.204	0	100.0
LEV	645	71.304	46.67	.67	395.45
SIZE	645	4.859	1.019	2.62	7.45

As shown in the Table 2, the number of observations is 645 (129 firms over 5 years). Board independence of the selected 129 companies shows an average value of 73 percent, ranging from about 17 percent to 67 percent. As per the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code (2018), Provision 2.2 specifies that independent directors should make up a majority of the Board. Table 1 shows that on the average, about 73% of the firms under consideration have complied. However, about 17 percent of the firms have not complied with the requirement of the Code, with respect to board independence.

Furthermore, board female gender of the selected 129 companies shows an average value of 16 percent, ranging from about 0 percent to 67 percent. As per the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code (2018), Provision 2.2 specifies that independent directors should make up a majority of the Board. Table 1 shows that on the average, about 73% of the firms under consideration have complied. However, about 17 percent of the firms have not complied with the requirement of the Code, with respect to board independence. Also, it is worthy to note that there are no specific legal requirements for gender diversity (i.e. Quota) in the Nigerian legal system except for regulations issued by the

Table 2 illustrates the descriptive statistic for board of directors' proxies such as board independence, board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership (shareholding), control variables (leverage and firm size) and the dependent variable (auditor choice).

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) Code of Corporate Governance, and the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance, 2018 (NCCG). CBN regulations mandate a minimum of 30 percent female representation on boards of Nigerian commercial banks, the SEC Code recommends that publicly listed companies consider gender when selecting board members, and the NCCG encourages the board to set diversity goals and to be mindful of them when filling board vacancies. On board size, the results in Table 1 show that board size averages 9 members, ranging from 3 to 21. However, the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code does not prescribe a minimum or maximum board size. It states that the Board should be of the correct size and have the best mix of skills to ensure its optimum effectiveness. However, it suggests that there should be balance of skills and diversity (including experience and gender) without compromising competence, independence and integrity. But, SEC recommends at least 5 members. In the instant case, on the average, the firms under consideration have 9 board members. Thus, in the NCCG, there is no specific indication about board size.

The average value of board meetings is 5 times in a year, ranging from once to 16 times. However, the Board is advised by the Code to meet at least once every quarter, totaling at least 4 times in a fiscal year. The average meetings for companies under consideration has met this requirement of the Code. Board ownership of the selected 129 companies shows an average value of 22 percent, ranging from about 0 percent to 100 percent, which is not in compliance with the Nigerian Corporate and Allied Matters Act (2020) threshold of 30%.

On the control variables, average value of the firms' leverage is 71 percent, and also ranging from 67 percent to 395 percent. These figure are considered to be extremely high and therefore require the attention of managers of the firms under consideration. Given these types of figures, they suggest that the firms under consideration are sitting on time bombs of debt. On firm size, the average is 4.859 points, and it ranges from 2.62 to 7.45 points, respectively.

Table 3 is a report of the results of correlation matrix, clearly showing the nexus between board of directors' characteristics and auditor choice. As indicated by the results in Table 3, the nexus between board independence and auditor choice is positive but not significant. Also, the nexus between board female gender and auditor choice is positive and significant. In the same manner, the nexus between board size and auditor choice is positive and significant. Also, the nexus between board meetings and auditor choice is positive and significant. However, the nexus between board ownership is negative, however, it is significant. Overall, it means that board female gender, board size, board meetings and board ownership show significant relationships with auditor choice. However, only board independence do not show significance with auditor choice.

On the status of the results of the control variables, leverage is negative and not significant. However, firm size is positive

and shows significant relationship with auditor choice. This significant result suggests that there is further need to conduct scenario analysis by dividing the dataset into large size firms and small size firms and compare and contrast the results. This is an area for further study, for scholars who may be interested in scenario analysis.

We also conduct a binary logistic regression analysis since the dependent variable of this study is measured by binary (1, or 0), in order to establish the effects of board of directors' characteristics on auditor choice. The results are reported in Table 4. As indicated, board independence is positive but not significant, meaning that it is not determinant of auditor choice. This result means that although, some directors are independent, they do not impact on the selection of external auditor(s).

Furthermore, board female gender is positive and significant, meaning that in the selection of external auditor(s), women directors play significant roles. In contrast, board size shows a positive and insignificant influence on the appointment of external auditor(s). However, board meetings show positive and significant effect on auditor choice. On board ownership, the effect is negative but significant. Overall, these results mean that only board of directors characteristics (board female gender, board meetings and board ownership) have significant effects on auditor choice in Nigeria. The results of board female gender and board meetings are consistent with our a priori expectations. However, the result on board ownership negative sign is not expected. It is expected that an increase in board ownership would serve as motivation for board members.

In terms of direction and quantity of effects, board female gender is positive and fit means that for every one unit increase in board female gender, auditor choice is made easy by 1.032 points. Similarly, for board meetings, the direction is also positive; every one meeting contributes to 1.304 points to auditor choice.

In the case of board ownership, the direction is negative; and for every unit increase in board ownership, the selection of external auditor is reduced by .979.

On control variables, only firm size is significant. It means that firm leverage is not important in the consideration of external auditor(s).

Table 3. Correlation Matrix of Board of Directors and Auditor Choice

Variable	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) BIG4	1.000							
(2) BI	0.073 (0.067)	1.000						
(3) BG	0.235* (0.000)	0.136* (0.001)	1.000					
(4) BS	0.353* (0.000)	0.054 (0.176)	0.115* (0.004)	1.000				
(5) BM	0.284* (0.000)	0.002 (0.951)	0.103* (0.010)	0.334* (0.000)	1.000			
(6) BO	-0.283* (0.000)	0.011 (0.776)	-0.007 (0.862)	-0.073 (0.064)	-0.058 (0.148)	1.000		
(7) LEV	-0.066 (0.093)	-0.065 (0.103)	0.053 (0.180)	-0.140* (0.000)	0.007 (0.864)	0.059 (0.138)	1.000	
(8) SIZE	0.539* (0.000)	-0.102* (0.010)	0.156* (0.000)	0.640* (0.000)	0.379* (0.000)	-0.221* (0.000)	-0.018 (0.657)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table 4. Logistic regression

AC	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val	p-val	[95% Co	Interval]	Sig
BI	1.012	.009	1.35	.178	.994	1.031	
BG	1.032	.008	3.93	0.000	1.016	1.049	***
BS	1.016	.048	0.34	.733	.926	1.115	
BM	1.304	.109	3.19	.001	1.108	1.535	***
BO	.979	.004	-5.49	0.000	.972	.986	***
LEV	.997	.002	-1.14	.255	.992	1.002	
SIZE	4.45	.782	8.49	0.000	3.153	6.281	***
Constant	0	0	-8.34	0.000	0	.001	***

Mean dependent var	0.571	SD dependent var	0.495
Pseudo r-squared	0.338	Number of obs	645
Chi-square	284.064	Prob > chi ²	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	573.279	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	608.665

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Based on the R-squared value, all the independent variables explain 33.8 percent of the total variation in auditor choice. In contrast, the remaining 66.2% impact is made by the factors not depicted in the model. Further, the results suggest that the p-value of the F-test is 0.000, which indicates the model is significant at the level of 99% and is highly reliable.

Overall, the results are consistent with previous studies on board female gender (Boukattaya & Omri, 2021; Dimitropoulos

& Koronios, 2021; Guizani & Abdalkrim, 2022; Lanis et al., 2017; Low et al., 2015; Oba & Fodio, 2013; Saeed et al., 2019; Simionescu et al., 2021; Solimene et al., 2017; Wang, 2020) and on board size (Bermig & Frick, 2010; Boone et al., 2007; Huther, 1997; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Mayur & Saravanan, 2005; Mayur & Saravanan, 2017; Ning et al., 2007; Ning et al., 2010; Saibaba & Ansari, 2012; Sarpal & Singh, 2013), on board meetings (Aanu et al., 2014; Al-Matari et al., 2014; Boesso et al., 2017; Chaudhary & Gakhar, 2018; Dalton & Dalton, 2005; Fariha et al., 2022; Kakanda & Salim,

2017; Narwal & Jindal, 2015; Rahman et al., 2019) and on board ownership (Alkurdi & Mardini, 2020; Audretsch & Lehmann, 2005; Barnhart & Rosenstein, 1998; Barontini & Bozzi, 2011; Darmadi & Gunawan, 2013; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Morck et al., 1986; Morck et al., 1988; Ng, 2005; Salehi & Baezegar, 2011).

V. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examines the relationship between board of directors' characteristics and auditor choice decisions of 129 NGX-listed companies. The sample period was five years, starting from 2017 to 2021. The study is based on data obtained from MachameRatios® database. The mean of auditor choice was 0.555; while the mean of board independence was 73 percent; board female gender was 15.5 percent; that of board size was 9 members; board meetings was 5 times in a year; and board ownership was 22 percent of equity holdings of the firms under consideration.

The correlation results show that board female gender, size, meetings and ownership are significant in relation to auditor choice. However, the binary logistic regression results show that only board female gender, board meetings and board ownership have significant effects on auditor choice decisions. Furthermore, it is important to note on the control variables, only firm size was significant, leverage was not significant in relation to auditor choice decisions.

Conclusively, external audit is a strong external corporate governance monitoring mechanism to protect the interest of the owners according to agency theory. The auditor choice research has paid more attention to the audit committee overall but has overlooked the unique agency context of auditor choice decisions. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of board of directors' characteristics on the auditor choice. These results have theoretical implications for the alignment and entrenchment hypotheses of the agency theory and practical implications for the regulators to improve the board of directors' characteristics and regulations.

In terms of recommendations, corporate stakeholders, such as regulators, shareholders, boards, and CEO/Managing Directors, market participants, and lenders, it is recommended, they should not waste time and money on ensuring board independence, it is not relevant in auditor choice decisions. Also, in terms of board female gender, stakeholders should ensure that women are well represented on corporate boards, in particular, regulators of non-banking sector, may consider to adopt the Central Bank of Nigeria rule of 30 percent women representation of boards of banks in Nigeria.

In terms of board size, stakeholders should not waste time and money to regulate on board size, as it is now, since it does not contribute to auditor choice decisions. On board meetings, there is average compliance, however, companies with less than four (4) meetings in a year should ensure compliance with minimum requirement. Regulators should implement the fines and sanctions on non-compliance with any of the Nigerian Corporate Governance Codes. Finally, on board ownership, stakeholders should reduce board shareholding percentage since it has negative significant effect on auditor choice decisions. This particular result is important, in order to avoid board members abusing their privileged of holding shares.

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